

A Comparative Study of Quinoline and Hexamethylene Tetramine Complexes with Ethereal Blue Perchromate in Relation to the Constitution of Blue and Red Perchromates

Ram Chandra Rai

Different samples of quinoline and hexamethylene tetramine complexes have been prepared with ethereal blue perchromate and analysed. Empirical and molecular formulae of the complexes suggest that the blue compound is chromium perchromate.

Two types of perchromates are known in the literature¹: (1) the blue and (2) the red perchromates. The blue perchromate is formed with the addition of 20 vol. hydrogen peroxide to a chromic acid or to an acidified chromate or dichromate solutions, which can be extracted with ether or other organic solvents². It forms complexes with nitrogenous organic bases giving solid compounds which can be filtered and washed. Red perchromate³ are obtained by adding 33% hydrogen peroxide to chromic acid or potassium dichromate or chromate solutions to which alkalis or organic nitrogenous bases are added in excess below—10° or more. Red precipitates are obtained which are filtered and washed with alcoholic solution or ether. These red perchromates were found prone to slow decomposition and the final product obtained after decomposition is yellow chromate. The formula for the potassium salt of the red perchromate was given by Riesenfeld as K_2CrO_6 .

On the basis of their analysis of the complexes of blue perchromate, O'Wiede⁴ gave $HCrO_5$ as the formula for the blue perchromate. This was supported by Riesenfeld⁵. However Schwarz and Giese⁶ on the strength of their experiment suggested the formula as CrO_5 for the blue perchromate.

Two points are very clear from what has been stated above that (1) there is only hexavalent chromium present in the red and blue perchromates and that (2) there appears to be no relation between the blue and the red perchromates as they differ in their methods of preparation.

While studying the change in pH of chromic acid solution with the addition of 20 vol. hydrogenperoxide, Bobtelsky *et. al.*⁷, Glasner⁸, Glasner and Steinberg⁹ and

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7. Bobtelsky, M., *et. al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 966.
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Evans¹⁰ have observed separately that two types of perchromates are obtained, one at or below pH 4 which is blue in colour and the other at or above pH 4.5 having violet colour. According to them there is a labile equilibrium between the two types of perchromates. Similar equilibrium has been observed between two compounds by Spitalaky¹¹ by conductometric method while studying the catalytic decomposition of chromic acid with hydrogen peroxide.

Rai¹², Pillai and Rai¹³, Rajput and Rai¹⁴ and Jagmer Singh and Rai¹⁵ on the basis of their studies on the ethereal and ethyl acetate extracted blue perchromate have found that chromium (III) is also present along with chromium (VI) in the constitution of blue perchromate.

The aim of this paper is just to show that ethereal blue perchromate contains chromium (III) along with chromium (VI) and that there exists a relation between ethereal blue and red perchromates.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation and Examination of quinoline complex:—Blue perchromate was prepared by taking 3.5% chromic acid solution (800 ml.) to which 450 ml. ether was added. The mixture was cooled in ice and to it 320 ml. of 20 vol. hydrogen peroxide also cooled in ice was added. The ethereal layer was separated by a separating funnel. The ethereal blue perchromate was taken in a cooled 500 ml. volumetric flask and the solution made to the mark with ice cooled ether. It was then kept in ice.

The ethereal blue perchromate was taken in a number of Erlenmeyer flasks and varying volumes of quinoline also cooled were added separately. After keeping these overnight the complexes were found to be precipitated. The precipitates were filtered separately and washed with 5% alcoholic solution till no yellow colouration was obtained and then finally washed with ether and dried in a desiccator over fused calcium chloride. Different samples were analysed separately.

Sample No. (50 ml. each)	A	B	C	D
Quinoline (added in ml.)	25	50	75	100

Estimation of Total Chromium:—Definite mass of each sample of the complex were taken separately in weighed silica crucibles and heated first slowly and then strongly. The complexes decomposed leaving Cr_2O_3 . These were weighed. Care was taken while heating as the complex was highly explosive.

Determination of the oxidation value of Quinoline Complex in NaOH solution in terms of volumes of N/20 sodium thiosulphate solution by iodometry:—Definite mass of each of the

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sample of the quinoline complex were taken and dissolved in 5 ml. of 1*N.* NaOH solution which was then made 100 ml.

The solution (25 ml. each) were taken and added to aqueous solutions of KI and acidified with dilute sulphuric acid. The liberated iodine was titrated against the standard solution of thiosulphate using starch solution as indicator.

Estimation of chromium in basic part as well as oxidation value of filtrates in terms of volume of N/20 sodium thiosulphate solution:—From the above 100 ml. solutions, 25 ml. aliquots were taken in separate beakers and in a bath of boiling water till green chromium hydroxide was completely precipitated. These were filtered over a gravimetric filter paper and washed with hot water till free from NaOH and chromate ions. These precipitates were then ignited in weighed silica crucibles and weighed as Cr₂O₃. This gave the amount of chromium present in the basic part of the complex.

The filtrates along with the washings were made distinctly acidic with dilute sulphuric acid and titrated iodometrically with N/20 thiosulphate solution using starch solution as indicator.

Estimation of Nitrogen in Quinoline complex:—This was carried out by Dumas's method. The percentage of nitrogen as well as quinoline are noted in the table below :—

TABLE I

Sample	% of N ₂	% of quinoline	% of total chromium	% of Cr in basic part	Vol. in ml. of thiosulphate N/20 used in titrating:	
					25 ml NaOH solution	filtrate from basic Cr
A	5.20	47.80	21.50	10.80	7.00	7.10
B	5.30	48.80	21.30	10.60	7.20	7.30
C	5.20	47.80	21.60	10.80	7.10	7.20
D	5.25	48.30	21.50	10.90	7.20	7.10

TABLE II

Change in colour	% of N ₂	% of hexamethylene tetramine complex	% of total chromium	Empirical Formula
Rose red	14.50	36.45	19.60	R ₂ CrO ₁₂
Red	15.90	39.80	15.00	R ₂ CrO ₁₀
Roddish yellow	17.50	43.80	16.50	R ₂ CrO ₈
Greyish	20.70	51.40	19.10	R ₂ CrO ₅
Yellow	22.00	54.90	20.30	R ₂ CrO ₄

Study of the Hexamethylene tetramine complex:—10 gms. of the hexamethylene tetramine was dissolved in 100 ml. of ethyl alcohol. Ethereal blue perchromate was prepared as above and taken in a jar glass bottle. To this ice cooled ethereal blue perchromate, 10 ml. of ice cooled alcoholic solution prepared above was added gradually. Complex formation immediately took place with a series of colour changes from blue, black, brown,

red and finally rose-red. The rose-red colour was obtained when the mixture was kept in an ice cooled bath for a long time. The complex was filtered very rapidly and washed with alcohol and finally with ether and then dried. It was observed that this complex was prone to decomposition and this took place in various stages, changing after fifteen days from rose red to yellow. This complex gave the blue perchromate with the addition of dilute sulphuric acid whereas those of pyridine, piperidine and quinoline did not. Moreover this complex liberated iodine from the aqueous potassium iodide whereas the quinoline complex fails to do so.

Estimation of Nitrogen and Hexamethylene Tetramine :—Nitrogen was estimated by Duma's method as done in the case of quinoline complex. The total chromium was also determined in the same way. Since the complex decomposes with hissing noise in water, therefore the amount of chromium (III) and chromium (VI) was not thought to be reliable in this case. The results are noted in table II where 'R' represents one molecule of hexamethylene tetramine.

DISCUSSION

The empirical formula for the quinoline complex is $R\text{CrO}_5$, where 'R' stands for one molecule of quinoline. From this formula it appears that there is no chromium (III) present in the molecule and the formula supports the formula of Schwarz and Giese. But if the chemical properties are seen i.e., when the complex is treated with sodium hydroxide, a green precipitate is obtained and the amount of Cr (III) in the complex is equal to Cr(VI) as shown in table I. This chemical behaviour of the complex clearly indicates the presence of Cr (III) in the complex. As the solution is strongly alkaline therefore, there appears no chance of Cr (VI) being reduced to trivalent state by the peroxy oxygen in the complex. From this it becomes quite clear that even from the quinoline complex the presence of Cr (III) along with the Cr (VI) is established in the constitution of the blue perchromate.

The amount of Cr (III) and Cr (VI) in the complex is equal as shown in table I. This clearly proves the formula CrCrO_8 which is one of the labile form of the blue perchromate as :—

The labile form CrCrO_8 is formed at higher pH and in the excess of hydrogen peroxide, whereas $\text{Cr}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_{10})_3$ form exists in water as well as at low pH.

From the perusal of the table II, it is quite evident that the hexamethylene tetramine complex has various empirical formulae, starting from $R'\text{CrO}_{11}$ to $R'\text{CrO}_4$, where 'R' represents one molecule of hexamethylene tetramine. It may be easily seen that although the quinoline complex as well as the hexamethylene tetramine complex are prepared from the ethereal blue perchromate but it is not only the colour which varies but also the chemical properties. With aqueous KI the hexamethylene tetramine complex liberates iodine, whereas quinoline complex does not have any effect. Moreover, when the two complexes are treated with dilute sulphuric acid, hexamethylene tetramine complex gives the blue perchromate if it has not attained the state $R'\text{CrO}_4$, whereas the quinoline complex does not give the blue perchromate. The properties exhibited by hexamethylene tetramine complex above shows that its behaviour is like red perchromates and that of the quinoline complex showing the properties of the blue perchromate. As both of the complexes have been prepared from the blue perchromate, therefore, it is quite easy to infer

that there exists a connection between the blue and red perchromates. The red perchromates decompose in water and in alkalis, therefore, the presence of chromium (III) in the compound is difficult to ascertain because the peroxy oxygen is capable of oxidising chromium (III) in chromium (VI) in aqueous as well as alkaline medium.

It may be seen from the table II that in the decomposition products of hexamethylene tetramine complex, one of them is $R'CrO_3$, similar to the empirical formula $R'CrO_3$. But the hexamethylene tetramine complex still has different chemical properties to those of the quinoline complex as it liberated iodine from the aqueous potassium iodide solution as well as that it gives blue perchromate with sulphuric acid (dilute) contrary to quinoline complex.

From all this it can be seen that there appears to be a structural change from the blue perchromate to red perchromate and that this appears to be unidirectional under ordinary circumstances. But when the dilute acids are added the red perchromate changes to the blue perchromate.

The empirical formula $R'CrO_{1.8}$ for the hexamethylene tetramine is not very strange as the compound of the formula $K_2CrO_{1.6}$ for the red perchromate has been reported. It is a well known fact that when ions from the transitional elements form complexes with organic molecules, then they are known to absorb extra oxygen atoms giving thus higher percentage of oxygen in the compound. Moreover in the red perchromate eight oxygen atoms are linked through oxygen atoms linkages. Similarly four more oxygen can be linked with as in the former compound. The instability of the compound can be explained as due to too many oxygen-oxygen linkages observed in red perchromates.

CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
UNIVERSITY OF SAUGAR,
SAGAR, M. P.

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